

CHEMISTRY OF BERYLLIUM. PART II. COMPOUNDS OF BERYLLIUM CHLORIDE WITH AMINES

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Amino complexes of BeCl_2 with primary, secondary and tertiary amines and diamines have been prepared and their constitution established. Viscometric measurements of β -naphthylamine and *o*-phenylenediamine in alcohol medium have also been made.

Among the ammoniates of BeCl_2 , prepared and studied by Ephraim (*Ber.*, 1912, 45, 1322) and Biltz (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1925, 148, 157), only $\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{NH}_3$ was found unusually stable towards heat, but it was easily decomposed by water (Sidgwick, "Chemical Elements and their Compounds", Vol. I, p. 208). Though Fricke and co-workers (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1924, 146, 103; 1925, 146, 121; 1926, 182, 347, 357; 1927, 163, 31; 1928, 170, 25; 1947, 253, 173) prepared a number of amine complexes (mostly primary amines) with beryllium chloride, but no systematic work was done on this subject.

The present investigation was therefore undertaken with a view to studying the formation of complex compounds of beryllium chloride with primary, secondary and tertiary amines and diamines.

EXPERIMENTAL

Beryllium chloride was prepared by the method of Pollok (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 86, 603). Excess of chlorine was removed by passing dry carbon dioxide. A solution of beryllium chloride, dissolved in dry ether, was used in all the experiments. Exact amount of beryllium chloride present in the solution was determined by estimating beryllium and chlorine in a known volume.

To a known volume of beryllium chloride solution, amine solutions in ether of approximately the same strength were added in slight excess with constant stirring. With all the primary and secondary amines the complex formed settled down immediately. In the case of diphenylamine only a slimy precipitate appeared on addition of the amine solution and the complex separated out in fine pink crystals after allowing the mixture to stand overnight in a desiccator (CaCl_2). It was washed with dry ether till free of amine (test: filtrate gave no precipitate with BeCl_2 solution). The precipitate was pressed between the folds of filter paper and finally dried in vacuum.

In the case of tertiary amines a slight turbidity appeared in the beginning but it disappeared on further addition of amine solutions. The excess of ether was then evaporated on a water-bath and the resulting mixture was allowed to stand in boiling water for 4 hours, cooled and the product washed free of excess of amine with dry ether. The compounds obtained with tertiary amines were very hygroscopic and hence they were quickly transferred to a vacuum desiccator and dried for 2-3 days. These were then analysed in a dry atmosphere.

TABLE I
Amine complexes of BeCl_2 .

S.No.	Amines	% Beryllium.		% Chlorine.		% Nitrogen.		Colour.	Formula.
		Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.		
1.	<i>o</i> -Anisidine	2.70	2.76	21.73	21.78	8.52	8.59	Light grey	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{O} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2$
2.	<i>p</i> -Anisidine	2.74	2.76	21.74	21.78	8.47	8.59	"	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{O} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2$
3	<i>o</i> -Phenetidine	2.52	2.54	20.04	20.06	7.88	7.91	"	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{O} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2$
4.	<i>p</i> -Phenetidine	2.53	2.54	20.11	20.06	7.88	7.91	"	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{O} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2$
5.	<i>m</i> -toluidine	3.07	3.06	24.10	24.14	9.47	9.50	"	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{NH}_2$
6.	Benzylamine	3.00	3.06	24.08	24.15	9.53	9.53	White	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{NH}_2$
7.	α -Naphthylamine	2.47	2.46	19.42	19.40	7.60	7.65	Light ash	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7 \cdot \text{NH}_2$
8.	β -	2.48	2.46	19.35	19.40	7.62	7.65	"	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7 \cdot \text{NH}_2$
9.	<i>p</i> -Phenylenediamine	4.72	4.77	37.77	37.77	14.81	14.89	Dark red	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2$
	Do (slight excess)	4.42	4.77	34.80	37.77	...	...	Blue	" " "
10.	1:2-Naphthylenediamine	3.78	3.78	29.78	29.79	11.71	11.76	Violet	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot \text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7(\text{NH}_2)_2$
11.	Dianisidine	2.80	2.78	21.96	21.91	8.53	8.61	Ash colour	$\text{BeCl}_2[\text{C}_6\text{H}_3(\text{OCH}_3)_2\text{NH}_2]_2$
12.	Ethylaniline	2.79	2.79	22.06	22.05	6.64	6.69	Light yellow	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$
13.	Benzylaniline	2.04	2.02	16.19	16.19	6.21	6.29	Grey	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot 2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5)$
14.	Diphenylamine	2.69	2.70	21.28	21.29	6.28	6.29	Pink, shining crystals	$2\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot 3(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5)$
15.	Dimethylaniline	2.78	2.79	22.04	22.05	8.57	8.69	Green	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$
16.	Diethylaniline	2.42	2.38	18.14	17.78	7.29	7.42	Pink	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2$
17.	<i>p</i> -aminodithylaniline	2.27	2.26	17.37	17.40	6.87	6.86	Black	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{NH}_2$
18.	" " "	3.59	3.69	28.38	29.14	...	...	Black	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2 \cdot \text{NH}_2$
19.	Ethylbenzylaniline	1.85	1.79	14.20	14.14	5.51	5.57	Brown	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{NCH}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$
20.	Trimethylamine	4.53	4.54	35.85	35.86	14.08	14.14	White	$\text{BeCl}_2 \cdot 3(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{N}$

-NH₂ - NH₂, and -N- groups and (ii) due to weak co-ordinating power of the nitrogen in these amine molecules. The divergence of colours from the original substance and also the deepening of colour in some of the compounds suggest that the complexes formed are of co-valent nature, as has been observed by Pitzer and Hildebrand (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 2475).

An attempt was made to arrive at the constitution of the amine complex by viscometric method but it was not successful. The viscosity was measured in alcoholic medium. Fig. 1 shows that there is a regular decrease in viscosity from BeCl₂ to

FIG. 1

β-naphthylamine and o-phenylenediamine as the proportion of amines is increased. From the curves it is evident that the complex formed with BeCl₂ and alcohol, BeCl₂.2EtOH (Fricke, *loc. cit.*), is very stable, and hence, the amine or diamine molecule is incapable of displacing the alcohol molecule as it happens in the case of BeCl₂.2Et₂O (Fricke, *loc. cit.*) where the ether molecule is replaced by amine molecules and the complex formed precipitates out.

That tertiary nitrogen has a weak co-ordinating power is further established by the fact that the tertiary amines form compounds only after heating BeCl₂ and amine mixtures on a water-bath for a long time.

In the case of *p*-aminodiethylaniline, when the ether solutions were mixed together, an immediate precipitate was formed having the composition BeCl₂.2A, but when heated with excess of BeCl₂, BeCl₂.A was obtained. The first compound is non-hygroscopic as in the case of compounds having -NH₂ group, and the second one is hygroscopic as in the case of compounds having N: group.

p-Phenylenediamine forms a dark red compound having the formula BeCl₂.C₆H₄(NH₂)₂, but when a slight excess of amine is added, the colour of the compound abruptly changes to blue and the compound obtained is not hygroscopic as the red compound. The percentages of Be and Cl were found lower than those in the case of the red compound, but no definite formula could be assigned to this compound.

It is interesting to note that diphenylamine affords a compound of the formula 2BeCl₂.3(C₆H₅NH.C₆H₅). It seems probable that the secondary nitrogen when directly attached to the bigger molecule offers steric hindrance whereby the octet of only one beryllium atom is complete and other remains incomplete.

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